

In the news – National

Kota Becomes the First City to Place Plaques Outside the Homes of Corneal Donor Families

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Kota became the first city in the country, to place a plaque outside the houses of corneal donor families, which has "I am proud to be an eye-donating family" scripted in golden letters.

This interesting awareness campaign was started by the Shine India Foundation, Rajasthan which has been continuously working for eye donation awareness, rights of the visually challenged, awareness about organ donation, body donation and skin donation in Hadoti division for the last 13 years.

Dr. Sangeeta Gaur, the founder secretary of the organization explained that the plaque is meant to inspire anyone visiting the house to consider eye donation. At the same time, it serves as a source of pride for the family, reminding them of their meaningful contribution.

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To cite : Sharma P, Suriyamoorthi S. Kota Becomes the First City to Place Plaques Outside the Homes of Corneal Donor Families. In the news. Indian Transplant Newsletter. 2024 Oct-Dec; 23(4):p3.

